

OPTIMIZATION OF MICROWAVE-INDUCED ROCK SOFTENING FOR KYRGYZ MINING APPLICATIONS

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Annotation: *This study investigated the use of microwave irradiation as a pretreatment (softening) method for various rock types. Representative samples of different mineral compositions (diorite, quartz, and phyllite) were exposed to a controlled 700 W microwave system operating at 2.45 GHz for durations ranging from 1 to 9 minutes, followed by cooling under different regimes. After irradiation, the samples were tested for uniaxial compressive strength and specific comminution energy to quantify the softening effect. Depending on mineralogy, the optimal exposure times were typically 3–5 minutes, yielding the greatest weakening of the rock and the largest reduction in grinding energy (up to about a 60% cut in specific energy requirements). Finally, analytical models and an empirical expression for residual stress distribution (post heating and cooling) were developed to relate irradiation time and temperature to subsequent comminution behavior. These results establish baseline conditions for effective microwave pretreatment of different ores.*

Key words: *Minerals; Rock; Granite; Energy; Microwave irradiation.*

Introduction:

Mining industry is a major component in the economies of many countries, including Kyrgyzstan. Mining sector, in fact, makes up 29% of Kyrgyzstan's total GDP (1) and over 60% of country's export (2). Global mining operations are highly energy-intensive, with ore crushing alone can consume around 30% of all the available energy (3). Given such energy burden, techniques such as microwave-assisted rock pretreatment, an innovative technology that can substantially transform energy efficiency in mining excavation, are urgently needed(4). Microwave pretreatment, more commonly known as microwave-irradiation, heats up the ore internally, causing thermal stress and creating a network of internal cracks, which make the ore more brittle and decrease its strength (5)(6)(7); The resulting brittleness significantly facilitates the subsequent mechanical grinding of ores, leading to a substantial energy savings and standing in contrast with more conventional heating methods(8)(9). Moreover, with high enough frequency and power, microwave irradiation has the potential to fully replace traditional methods, which could substantially decrease the energy needs for ore grinding and completely transform the mining industry (10). Considering all of this, for countries heavily contingent on mining industry -such as Kyrgyzstan- it is essential to explore the optimal parameters for the effective microwave pretreatment of different rocks and minerals (11). High-power microwave systems are continuously being built and studied (12). Globally, numerous studies have analyzed the effects of different conditions of irradiation on local ores to evaluate its possible applications, and the results so far been highly encouraging: Microwave exposure has shown substantial ecological and economics benefits, especially in the concrete and construction industries, where it can significantly reduce energy consumption and ameliorate material recycling (13)(14)(15). Hence, as microwave pretreatment features advantages that can rectify industry's problems related to ecology, energy efficiency, and mineral processing, determining optimal conditions for rock samples from Kyrgyzstan's mines could provide a pathway to lower production costs, minimize environmental impact, and, possibly, completely transform local economy.

The application of microwave irradiation in the mining industry has been studied for several decades, with pioneer work by Soviet researchers in the 1970s establishing the foundation for experimental investigation into high-energy electromagnetic heating for rock weakening and breakage (16). It was the study at the Institute of Geotechnical Mechanics of the Academy of

Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR in 1987 that considerably advanced the idea of microwave irradiation for rock grinding purposes. This work first showed how microwave-assisted breakage works: Microwaves induce different differential thermal expansions between ore minerals and matrix, causing microcracks along grain boundaries (17). Several laboratory experiments were done throughout the CIS and not only, demonstrating how microwave exposure leads to the formation of microcracks and softening, which leads to a markedly lower grinding energy requirements (18) (17) (19) (20). In around 1990s-2000s works by the western researchers, particularly in the UK and Canada, began to produce parallel findings, confirming that microwave irradiation reduces ore's strength and grinding energy. For instance, Kingman et al(1999) studied the influence of microwave radiation on Norwegian ilmenite ores, concluding that high power treatments were most effective and brought a reduction in work index of up to 90%. This was attributed to, again, an extensive microfracturing, as well as improved liberation of mineral grains (21). In Canada, microwave pretreatment of nickel ore achieved approximately 46.5% grinding energy savings compared with the conventional process of comminution (22).

In summary, consistent results across decades and region validate the use of microwave pretreatment as one of the most energy-efficient and exciting methods of ore weakening and comminution. Given the mineralogical complexity of Kyrgyzstan's deposits - particularly those at Kumtor, Makmal, and Toktozan – and the country's dependence on mining exports, microwave pretreatment holds a promising future as a locally scalable, energy-efficient alternative to conventional processing of ores. Moreover, due to economic problems and climate change, Kyrgyzstan's energy resources become increasingly limited every year: Majority (around two-thirds of) country's energy resources come from the hydroelectric power, while the remaining domestic demand is usually met through energy imports (23). During dry years or winter months, however, water levels in reservoirs considerably drop, leading to electricity shortages and heavier reliance on imported fuel-based energy sources (24). In such conditions, lowering energy demand for ore comminution could significantly improve Kyrgyzstan's energy resilience. Hence, establishing optimum irradiation parameters tailored to Kyrgyzstan's ores is not only scientifically relevant but may also offer numerous economic benefits.

Experiment and process:

In the classic study by E.B. Abkin, the outcomes of crushing iron ores that were pre-treated by three different methods were compared: A)heating with microwave irradiation up to 300 °C, B)heating in a muffle furnace to the same temperature, and C)Control group (no thermal pretreatment). Results have shown that ore samples exposed to microwave irradiation produce a significantly higher yield of fine particles. After the microwave pretreatment, the fraction of particles sized 0.074 mm increased by 6–10%, and with longer treatment durations this increase reached 25%. In contrast, heating in a muffle furnace showed no significant change. Such results are explained by an enhanced opening of grains due to microwave exposure, which facilitate subsequent comminution. Tests at various temperatures confirmed this effect. At 35 W/cm², treatment for 1–10 minutes boosted efficiency in the 10–0.05 mm range by up to 60%, with higher power enabling shorter exposure times (25) (26). To look at the optimal parameters of microwave exposure for local rocks, representative ore samples from Kyrgyz deposits were subjected to controlled microwave pretreatment.

Samples photo:

At the start, the free-fall drop-weight method was used to crush ore in order to determine the impact strength coefficient. Three common rock types (Toktozan diorite, Makmal quartzite, and Kumtor phyllite) were collected and prepared into 30 batches, each consisting of 5 pieces of ore with the diameters of 20-25mm. For each complete measurement, 5 such portions were used. The results obtained using this methodology are characterized by a relatively low and insignificant coefficient of variation, averaging about 10–15%. To confirm the results and obtain a reliable mean value, the experiments were repeated 5 times.

To determine the strength coefficient, a specialized device called POK was developed, composed of a vertical tubular drop tower and a fine-fraction volumetric cylinder. Each portion of the sample was crushed in the cup of a tubular drop tower by a 2.4 kg weight dropped from the height of 600 mm. If it is necessary to vary the amount of energy applied during crushing, this is achieved by changing the amount of weight drops acting on the object. Typically, for rocks of low to medium strength 3-15 drops were applied. For most rock and coal samples, the relationship between the dust yield, expressed as l (the height of the fine-fraction column in the volumetric cylinder), and the crushing work A tends to stabilize at high values of A . Therefore, for each tested rock, the number of impacts was adjusted so that the dust yield l remained within 20 to 70 mm. The weight and drop height were kept constant throughout the tests.

Diagrams from the experimental design:

After crushing, the resulting fines were emptied from the cup into a 0.5 mm sieve. Five individual crushed portions were sieved separately. The fraction finer than 0.5 mm was collected and poured into a volumetric cylinder (with the 23 mm diameter), and the height of the dust column was measured.

The strength index of the rock was calculated as the ratio of mechanical energy input during crushing to three newly created surface area, using the formula developed by M.M. Protodyakonov Jr: (27)

$$\hat{E} = \frac{nE_i}{V} \quad \text{or} \quad K = \frac{n \cdot mgh}{Sl}$$

Where:

E – energy of a single impact;

V – volume of the <0.5 mm fraction;

m – mass of the falling weight;

g – acceleration due to gravity;

n – number of impacts applied to a single portion;

l – height of the dust column in the volumetric cylinder (mm);

h – drop height of the weight;

S – cross-sectional area of the volumetric cylinder.

(The mean value of 5 such calculated values is taken as the result)

Picture of pieces:

It was found that after crushing brittle materials, about 90% of the newly created surface area was made up of very fine particles (<0.5mm). Hence, to simplify evaluation after crushing, only the surface of this fine fraction was considered. The height of dust column in the cylinder, in this case, was assumed to be proportional to the total surface area of fine particles.

Subsequently, with the use of a laboratory-grade microwave oven, the effects of microwave exposure time on the specific comminution energy were investigated. Ore samples were treated using a laboratory-grade 700 W, 2450 MHz microwave oven with an effective cavity volume of 0.03 m³. The specimens weighed 200–250 g and consisted of fragments sized 20-25mm. Exposure durations ranged from 1 to 9 minutes in 1-minute increments, and up to 20 minutes with 2-5-minute intervals in the extended series. Following irradiation, all samples were cooled under ambient air conditions to ensure consistent thermal gradients.

Diagram of the oven:

Specific comminution energy was calculated before and after microwave exposure at varying durations. Based on this data, graphs were plotted for each ore type showing the relationship between exposure time and energy consumption. As shown by figures 1.1-1.3, optimal microwave exposure duration differs for each sample due to varying mineral compositions: (28)

3 minutes for Toktozan diorite;

3 minutes for Kumtor gray phyllite;

5 minutes for quartz from the Vostochny–Kounrad site.

At those durations, largest softening effect is seen without unnecessary energy expenditure.

Dependence of the specific energy consumption of ore comminution on the duration of microwave exposure (diorite, Toktozan deposit)

Dependence of the specific energy consumption of ore comminution on the duration of microwave exposure (grey phyllite, Kumtor deposit)

Dependence of the specific energy consumption of ore comminution on the duration of microwave exposure (Eastern–Kounrad deposit).

For microwave pretreatment to be economically feasible, the energy savings during grinding must exceed consumed during irradiation. It was demonstrated that optimal durations can reduce both soften the sample and reduce specific energy comminution by a factor of 2-2.5, leading to massive net energy savings. Additional benefits are:

- reduced wear of milling components due to lower ore strength, decreasing metal consumption and maintenance costs;
- previously mentioned improved liberation of valuable minerals, which increased the overall extraction efficiency. (25)

To demonstrate net energy savings, an example of diorite from Toktozan deposit can be taken. Its untreated specific energy comminution energy is 87 J/cm³. After 3 minutes of irradiation, this value decreased to 30 J/cm³.

Hence, the energy consumed by the microwave oven (0.7 kW) during a 3-minute exposure is:
 $0.7 \times 0.05 \text{ h} = 0.035 \text{ kWh}$,

or

$$35 \text{ Wh} \times 3.6 \times 10^3 = 126,000 \text{ J.}$$

Given the cavity volume of 30,000 cm³, the specific microwave energy input is:

$$126,000 / 30,000 = 4.2 \text{ J/cm}^3.$$

Thus, the total specific comminution energy after irradiation is:

$$30 + 4.2 = 34.2 \text{ J/cm}^3.$$

The overall energy savings relative to the untreated state amount to:

$$87 - 34.2 = 52.8 \text{ J/cm}^3,$$

$$52.8 / 87 = 0.607,$$

i.e., 60.7%.

In contrast to the Toktozan diorite- and other heterogeneous polymineral ores- homogenous rocks, such as Makmal metasamotite and quartz from Vostochny–Kounrad, exhibit only a small reduction in comminution energy. Meanwhile, , heterogeneous polymineral ores-Toktozan diorite and Kumtor gray phyllite-show reductions of up to 2.5 times. Similarly, studies have shown that in a microwave irradiated granite, highest thermal stress is concentrated at a grain boundaries plagioclase (Pl) and quartz (Qtz). Altogether, experimental results and studies further confirm that mineralogical heterogeneity, which facilitates the formation of microcracks, is the key factor enabling effective weakening under microwave irradiation. (28) (29)(30).

Additionally, effects of cooling conditions after irradiation were also investigated. Two regimes were compared:

- cooling in ambient air,
- rapid cooling in cold water (quenching).

The results, shown in the table 1, illustrate that under water quenching the minimum specific comminution energy is reached at a shorter exposure durations. This indicates that thermal shock enhances microcrack formation. (31) Following graphs represent how water-cooled samples air-cooled samples respond to changes microwave exposure duration in terms of crushing strength and specific comminution energy.

Dependence of the ore strength coefficient on the duration of microwave exposure (metasamotite, Makmal deposit, air-cooled)

Dependence of the ore strength coefficient on the duration of microwave exposure (metasamotite, Makmal deposit, water-cooled)

Dependence of the specific comminution energy on the duration of microwave exposure (metasamotite, Makmal deposit, air-cooled)

Dependence of the specific comminution energy on the duration of microwave exposure (metasamotite, Makmal deposit, water-cooled)

Analytical work:

As noted, microwave irradiation softens strong ores, reducing the mechanical resistance of ores in subsequent processing stages. Under mechanical load, it usually occurs by 2 main modes:

- Tensile fracturing (detachment): breaking by volume expansion or tensile stress.
- Shear sliding: failure by shear along planes.

Rocks exhibit higher strength under compression than under tension, following the empirical relation:

$$\sigma_o > \sigma_c > \tau_s > \sigma_t$$

Where:

σ_o is triaxial compressive strength; σ_c is uniaxial compressive strength; τ_s is shear strength; σ_t is the rock's uniaxial tensile strength. Other important factors are brittleness and resistance. The brittleness coefficient K_b and its reciprocal K_s are defined as:

$$K_b = \sigma_c / \sigma_p$$

$$K_s = \sigma_p / \sigma_c$$

It is obvious that highly brittle rocks (with large K_b) have small K_s .

Analytical expression for Comminution Energy

To model how microwave-induced stresses affect the energy needed to crush (comminute) the rock, we consider the specific comminution energy E_V (energy per unit volume) after irradiation relative to the original E_{V0} , the following relation is proposed:

$$E_V = E_{V0} + E_{V0} K_s$$

Where:

E_{V_0} is the comminution energy of the untreated rock, and K_s is an energy coefficient depending on stress. If the rock's effective stress parameter exceeds the material's resistance (specifically, if the residual stress σ_0 is tensile and large), then K_s becomes negative and the rock is easier to crush (E_V decreases)

Building on the experimental observations, detailed analysis shows that crushing involves combined micro-detachment and shear at grain boundaries. An analytic model was derived by defining:

$$K_s = \frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_c} - \frac{3 \cdot |\sigma_0|}{\sigma_c} \quad (\text{equation 1})$$

Substituting into the energy equation yields:

$$E_V = E_{V_0} \left[1 + \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_c} - \frac{3 \cdot |\sigma_0|}{\sigma_c} \right) \right] \quad (\text{equation 2})$$

It can be seen that when σ_0 is tensile ($\sigma_0 > 0$), the expression $(\sigma_t - 3\sigma_0)$ decreases, and consequently E_V becomes lower than E_{V_0} . In contrast, compressive residual stress ($\sigma_0 < 0$) leads to an increase in E_V

Residual Stress and Temperature equation:

Microwave heating induces internal thermal stresses in the rock that depend on the peak temperature reached and the cooling regime. The characteristic temperatures T_m and T_2 relative to the mineral decomposition temperature T_p were assumed to be proportional to the average residual stress. In practice, the following piecewise relations was adopted:

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{T_m}{T_p} \pm \frac{T_2}{T_m} \right) 2\sigma_p \quad (\text{equation 3})$$

Where:

T_m is the temperature at which the specific comminution energy is minimal (i.e. the point of stress sign reversal); T_2 is the temperature reached at exposure time; T_p is the decomposition temperature of the main mineral; and Q_p is the rock's uniaxial tensile strength. For the equation 3, the plus sign (+) is used when $T_m > T_2$, in which case predominantly tensile residual stresses are formed. The minus sign (-) is used when $T_m < T_2$, in which case predominantly compressive residual stresses are formed.

Using derived model (equations 1-3) and experimental parameters, the specific comminution energy for the studied rocks was calculated. First, the case of Kumtor dark-gray phyllite can be considered. The untreated specific energy of the phyllite is $E_{V_0} = 97 \text{ J/cm}^3$, and its uniaxial compressive strength is $\sigma_c = 1112 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$ (Table 2.3.1). The primary mineral of this phyllite is calcite, with a decomposition temperature $T_p = 900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 2.3.2); the phyllite's tensile strength is $\sigma_p = 56 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$ (Table 2.3.1)

During the experiment, the minimum comminution energy was found to occur after 3 min of irradiation, corresponding to $T_m = 356 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; meanwhile, at 1 min irradiation $T_2 = 310 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Substituting those values into equation 3 gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_0 &= \left(\frac{T_m}{T_p} + \frac{T_2}{T_m} \right) \cdot 2\sigma_p = \left(\frac{356}{900} + \frac{31}{356} \right) 56 \cdot 2 = \\ &= (0,396 + 0,0871) \cdot 112 = 54 \text{ kgf/cm}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Using this value in equation 2, post-treatment comminution energy becomes:

$$E_V = E_{V_0} + E_{V_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_c} - \frac{3 \cdot |\sigma_0|}{\sigma_c} \right) = 97 + 97 \left(\frac{56}{1112} - \frac{3 \cdot |54|}{1112} \right) = 87,7 \text{ J/cm}^3.$$

Following the same procedure for other durations of exposure, residual stress changes to:

$E_V=72 \text{ J / cm}^3$ (2 minutes);

$E_V=61 \text{ J/cm}^3$ (3 minutes);

$E_V=77 \text{ J/cm}^3$ (4 minutes);

$E_V=70 \text{ J/cm}^3$ (5 minutes);

$E_V=64,4 \text{ J/cm}^3$ (6 minutes);

$E_V=60 \text{ J/cm}^3$ (7 minutes);

$E_V=58 \text{ J/cm}^3$ (8 minutes).

These values closely align with empirical observations, as illustrated in the next figure

Comparison of the experimental (1) and analytical (calculated) (2) dependencies of the specific comminution energy for Grey Phyllite from the Kumtor deposit.”

A similar procedure was applied to quartz from East Konrad deposit. The quartz’s decomposition temperature is 1470°C and its tensile strength is 60 kgf/cm^2 . The minimal comminution energy appeared at $T_m=702^\circ\text{C}$ after 5 minutes of microwave exposure. After 1-minute $T_2=91^\circ\text{C}$. Applying these to Eq. 3 yields:

$$\sigma_0 = \left(\frac{T_m}{T_p} + \frac{T_2}{T_m} \right) 2\sigma_p = \left(\frac{702}{1470} + \frac{91}{702} \right) 60 * 2 =$$

$$= (0,4776 + 0,1296) * 120 = 73 \text{ kgf / cm}^2.$$

With an initial comminution energy of $E_{V0}=69 \text{ J/cm}^3$ and compressive strength $\sigma_c=1750 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$, the treated energy at 1 minute becomes:

$$E_V = E_{V0} + E_{V0} \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_c} - \frac{3*|\sigma_0|}{\sigma_c} \right) = 69 + 69 \left(\frac{60}{1750} - \frac{3*|73|}{1750} \right) = 69 + 69 (0,034 - 0,1251)$$

$$= 69 - 6,3 = 62,7 \text{ J / cm}^3 .$$

For longer times, the model predicts $E_V= 58, 55, 52, 50.4, 62.4,$ and 61 J/cm^3 for 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 min, respectively.

Likewise, those computed values strongly correlate with empirical observations, as illustrated in the next figure.

All analytical and experimental E_V values for each rock are displayed in the table 5. The mean deviation between these values is on the order of only 5–10 %, which validates the accuracy of the proposed model.

Dependence of specific energy consumption of grinding on microwave exposure time (quartz, East-Kounrad), 1- experimental; 2- calculated

Comparison of experimental (1) and analytical (2) specific comminution energy curves for quartz from the Eastern–Kounrad deposit.

Energy consumption analysis:

The reductions in grinding energy are substantial, as shown above. However, it is vital to assess whether the energy consumed during heating offsets these gains. To address this, The total specific energy - combining irradiation and grinding - was calculated.

Microwave input energy is computed by:

$$E_t = N \cdot t$$

where $N=700N$ (Oven power) and t is the exposure time in seconds. For instance, for a 1-minute treatment:

$$E_t = 700 \cdot 60 = 42,000 \text{ J.}$$

The volume-specific thermal energy is, $E_{TV} = E_t / V_e$

Where the effective volume $V_e = 0.7 \times 30,000 = 21000 \text{ cm}^3$ (as only 70% of the 30 L oven can be filled).

Hence, for duration of 1 minute,

$$E_{TV} = 42000 / 21000 = 2 \text{ J/cm}^3.$$

Likewise, values for other durations can be calculated. They were shown in the following table 6

Using these values, the total specific energy was calculated for each stage. Figure below plots the experimental comminution energy (curve 1) and the total energy (curve 2) for the Aktatyr limestone as a function of microwave duration. It demonstrates that the total energy (curve 2) never exceeds the experimental value, confirming that optimal microwave pretreatment leads to a net energy gain.

Relationship between specific energy consumption for grinding and microwave exposure time (limestone from Ak-Tatyr deposit. 1-experimental; 2-total considering the sum of energy consumption on microwave radiation

Graphs of the specific comminution energy of limestone from the Ak-Tatyr deposit:

- 1 — experimental data;
- 2 — cumulative (total) values.

Discussions:

Kyrgyzstan's heavy reliance on energy-intensive mining, as well as its problems in generating enough energy, makes any reductions in crushing and grinding energy critically important. The experimental results demonstrated that microwave-pretreatment substantially improves the comminution behavior of various Kyrgyz ores. The mineralogically heterogeneous samples, such as Toktozan diorite and Kumtor phyllite, experienced a particularly notable reduction in specific comminution energy, reaching up to 2.5-fold compared to the original material. This behavior is attributed to enhanced internal microcrack formation caused by differential thermal expansion between mineral phases during irradiation, as well as increased residual tensile stress concentration at grain boundaries.

Cooling regime also proved to be a critical parameter. Water quenched samples achieved their minimum specific comminution energy at shorter microwave exposure durations. In doing so, they illustrated that rapid water cooling produced deeper damage more quickly, promoting fracture initiation and propagation within the ore structure.

These findings are especially relevant in the context of Kyrgyzstan's energy system. Given the mining sector's importance and its large share of national electricity consumption, technologies that reduce ore grinding demands are essential, especially considering the country's vulnerability to seasonal energy shortages. The illustrated energy savings- up to 60% in some cases-suggest that microwave pretreatment could serve as a practical way for improving the energy efficiency and throughput of Kyrgyz mining operations, especially in remote or energy-constrained regions.

Conclusion:

Optimal exposure times varied by rock type:

- 3 min for Toktozan diorite and Kumtor gray phyllite.
- 5 min for Vostochny-Kounrad quartzite.

These durations produced maximum weakening with minimal energy input.

Specific comminution energy decreased substantially post-irradiation:

- Toktozan diorite's specific comminution energy dropped from 87 J/cm³ to 30 J/cm³ after 3 minutes.

- Net energy savings reached 60.7% when accounting for microwave energy input.

Cooling conditions affected outcomes:

- Water quenching resulted in faster weakening than air cooling.
- Thermal shock intensified microcrack formation and improved grindability.

Mineralogical heterogeneity was a key factor:

- Heterogeneous ores responded more effectively to microwave exposure.
- Homogeneous rocks like Makmal metasamotite showed less energy reduction.

Analytical model results matched experimental data closely:

- The calculated residual stress and comminution energy aligned within around 5–10% of measured values.

- This validates the theoretical framework relating stress state to energy consumption.

In conclusion, it was confirmed that the microwave pretreatment is a viable method for significantly reducing the energy required for rock comminution in Kyrgyz mining conditions.